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IMAGE OF TOURIST DESTINATION: REVIEW AND ANALYSIS OF ARTICLES PUBLISHED IN BRAZIL

Abstract. *The tourist destination image is recognized by many scholars in the area as one of the main factors responsible for influencing the tourist's choice of destination and, therefore, an essential factor to be considered in destination tourism management and planning, in order it can be sustainably competitive. The aim of this article is to conduct a systematic review of articles published in Brazil on the subject of destination image to provide an overview of how studies on the subject are being carried out. To this end, the SPELL platform was used to identify and collect the data. The sample of this study was compound by 23 articles existing on SPELL database, published between the years 2008 and 2020. Most of the articles studied are characterized as exploratory-descriptive research, empirical in nature, balancing between quantitative and qualitative methodological approaches. The main publications that serve as a basis for destination image studies were identified: Baloglu and MacCleary (1999); Echtner and Ritchie (1991); Gallarza, Saura and García (2002); Beerli and Martín (2004) and Chagas (2008). The results of this study seek to contribute to the scientific development about the tourist destination image serving as a basis to guide future studies on the subject and, consequently, to contribute to the development of tourist destinations.*

Keywords: *image, tourist destinations, tourist destination image, bibliographic review*

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ИМИДЖ ТУРИСТСКОЙ ДЕСТИНАЦИИ: АНАЛИТИЧЕСКИЙ ОБЗОР БРАЗИЛЬСКИХ НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ

В статье рассматривается сущность и значение маркетинга в социальных медиа для продвижения туристских услуг в онлайн-среде. Цель исследования – определить перспективные пути увеличения целевой аудитории при помощи сообществ в социальных сетях, адаптированных для туризма. Основными методами исследования являются системный и ситуационный подход, классификация, формально-логический анализ и кабинетное исследование. На основе обзора литературы о подходах к пониманию видов социальных сообществ и важности правильного позиционирования рекламных объявлений в формировании лояльности к территориальному брендингу клиентов авторы представляют авторское определение «сообщество в социальной сети», приводят классификацию существующих сообществ, раскрывают особенности каждого из типов. Практическая ценность исследования заключается в разработке направлений использования преимуществ каждого из типа социальных сообществ для развития туризма на локальных территориях. Авторами приводятся практические инструменты для работы по выявлению и агрегированию целевой аудитории в популярных в России социальных сетях. Основными направлениями дальнейших исследований являются сравнительный анализ лучших практик использования социальных сообществ в туризме с целью эффективного взаимодействия с целевой аудиторией и разработка рекомендаций по контент-плану маркетинговой стратегии продвижения территориального бренда и туристических продуктов конкретной локальной рекреации.

Ключевые слова: туризм, целевая аудитория, маркетинг в социальных сетях, сообщество, таргетированная реклама, территориальный брендинг

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Introduction

Tourism is a social phenomenon that promotes the individual's escape from everyday life and the stress of the busy contemporary life (Scalabrini et al., 2015). Because of its relevance, tourism has even been indicated as the first sector of the world economy (Ansa-rah, 2002; Pérez-Nebra et al., 2010) with a steady growth rate year by year, at least until the arrival of the COVID19 pandemic at the end of the year 2019. In 2018 it generated revenues to the tune of \$1.7 trillion, driving job creation, serving as a catalyst for innovation and entrepreneurship, and thus contributing to the transformation and development of entire communities (World Tourism Organization, 2019). Tourism is an activity that, when well-planned and managed, attracts investments, mobilizes the service sector, and values the local culture (Mota, 2001). That is, the tourist activity is able to promote local and regional development, in addition to, value the local identity and preserve the historical, cultural and natural heritage.

Globalization, a consequence of the technological development of means of communication and transport, has created a scenario of fiercer competition among tourist destinations and, consequently, demanded a form of tourism development that makes them competitive with competing destinations. For Añaña et al. (2016); Chagas (2009) and Scalabrini et al. (2015) the success in the development of a tourist destination is in the image that it passes to its visitors or potential visitors, due to the need that tourists have to decide which destination they will visit even before the trip, without the possibility of direct contact with the place before the choice. This fact highlights the importance of the image that the tourist has of the destination in his decision process (Santos et al., 2015).

Thus, the tourist destination image is recognized by many scholars in the area as one of the main factors responsible for influencing the tourist's choice of destination (Añaña et al., 2016; Arruda et al., 2020; Campos et al., 2013; Carvalho et al., 2016; Chagas, 2008, 2009; Chagas et al., 2013; Ferreira et al.,

2019; Machado et al., 2010; Martichiello et al., 2016; Pérez-Nebra et al., 2010; Santana et al., 2017, 2018; Santos et al., 2015; Santos et al., 2018; Scalabrini et al., 2015, 2018; Carniello et al., 2012; Silva et al., 2012), as well as, their behavior, satisfaction, loyalty, and their recommendation to others regarding the tourist destination. Therefore, the image is a factor of paramount importance to be considered in the destination's tourism management and planning, as a means of creating a positive image and differentiating itself from other destinations, in order to remain sustainably competitive (Arruda et al., 2020; Chagas, 2009; Chagas et al., 2013; Scalabrini et al., 2015).

The image of a place perceived by a tourist can differ significantly from the image of a resident (Santana et al., 2018). It becomes essential to know the vision of local actors about the place where they live and about the development of local tourism, according to the principles of sustainability of community-based and creative tourism. In these approaches the tourism activity is not seen only as an economic activity. It aims to develop sustainable tourism with the inclusion of the local community in the policies and governance plans of tourism activity. In this way, the negative impacts of tourism are minimized and the generation of benefits for the local society is promoted, with the valorization of the community by the community itself, resulting from the sense of belonging and self-esteem of the population for its own identity (Emmen-dorfer et al., 2021; Richards, 2020; Habert et al., 2016; Moraes et al., 2015; Jamal et al., 1995). The closer the image perceived by the tourist is to the image that the inhabitant has of the place where he lives, the more realistic this image will be, because it presents an image that represents the local identity.

In this context, by understanding how the image of the destination is formed, it is possible to work it in the best way in favor of the destination and its community, contributing effectively to the sustainable development of tourism. Thus, the objective of this work is to carry out a systematic review of

articles published in Brazil on the image of tourist destinations to provide an overview of how the studies on the subject are being carried out. As a specific objective, a synthesis of the theoretical bases of the tourist destination image construct that were presented in the articles selected for this study was carried out, as follows in the next topic.

Tourist Destination Image

For Santaella et al. (2001) the study of image can be divided into 2 domains: the image as a visual representation - drawings, paintings, engravings, photographs, among others - and; the subjective domain of the human mind image as a mental representation. Destination image is a complex construct, because it has an interdisciplinary approach that covers different areas of knowledge such as anthropology, sociology, geography, psychology and marketing, in this way, attracting researchers from various areas to the study of the subject (Campos et al., 2013; Gallarza et al., 2002; Scalabrini et al., 2015). Given this, there is no consensus among scholars on the subject as to a single conceptualization of destination image, being found several approaches.

Chagas (2008) analyzed different conceptualizations of destination image carried out by several authors (Acerenza, 2002; Big-nami, 2002; VAZ, 1999; Ituassu, 2004; Echtner et al., 1991; Kotler et al., 1994; Gallarza et al., 2002, Chagas, 2007; Ries et al., 1996) and pointed out the most relevant points among them. From this analysis it was possible to consider that the destination image consists in a mental representation that one has of a certain tourist destination from a set of impressions about it, and it can be a future projection or a past memory, result of human perception and, therefore, characterized by a great subjectivity.

In this context, the tourist has a great involvement in the choice of destination. He creates predictions and expectations before traveling, and his decision for a destination depends on the favorable image he has of the place. This image is based on internal factors, his culture, memory, previous knowledge or

arising from past experiences, and factors of the external environment, such as comments from family, friends and third parties, information coming from advertisements and the media in general (Ferreira et al., 2019; Pérez-Nebra et al., 2010).

It is important to emphasize the influence of the internet, especially the social media in the construction of the image for being, currently, protagonists in the generation of information about tourist destinations, through direct and spontaneous online communication between consumers, the electronic Word-Of-Mouth [eWOM - electronic Word-Of-Mouth]. For example, the Tripadvisor platform, one of the main online portals on tourism, where tourists make comments and evaluations of destinations around the world (Ar-ruda et al., 2020). As well as institutional websites that can influence the formation of this mental image about the destination (Carvalho et al., 2016).

Thus, the formation of the image and the creation of the expectation occurs even before the actual experience, the visit *in loco* to get to know the place. It is then realized that the image that the individual has about a certain destination is the main factor of decision in the choice of the place that will visit. From this image, “[...] new images are accumulated, modified and redefined, also influencing post-visit behavioral intentions” (Bigne et al., 2001; Castro et al., 2007; Chen et al., 2007; Hallmann et al., 2015; Nisco et al., 2015; Smith et al., 2015 apud Santana et al., 2017). Because the image evolves over time, it is important to work on it so that the image of the destination does not fall into the base of outdated and inappropriate stereotypes and, consequently, cause negative consequences in the short and long term. Thus, it is important that the image is evaluated and worked in order to make it positive and attractive to the public (Carvalho et al., 2016).

Therefore, in the current scenario where people get more and more information, especially through the internet, tourist destinations demand the adoption of marketing strategies to project a positive and unique

image to differentiate from its competitors and remain competitive (Añaña et al., 2016; Baloglu et al., 1999), since the “[...] tourist’s decision to purchase a particular travel destination is based on a mental construction of the places, and marketing plays an important mediating role in projecting the desired image for the destination. [...]” (Machado et al., 2010). Also, one must consider that the heterogeneity of the demand, of different tourist profiles with different experiences, generates a diversity of images for the same destination (Pérez-Nebra et al., 2010; Ruschmann, 1990).

Chagas (2008) summarizes the possible image types by analyzing the work of other authors, and from this it is possible to characterize the image of a destination as follows: positive or negative (Bignami, 2002); positive, negative and neutral (Mendonça Júnior, 2004); confusing or stereotyped (Vaz, 1999); and, poor, mixed, contradictory, overly attractive (Haider; Kotler; Rein, 1994), as shown in Table 1.

Although the studies and works about destination image focus mainly on the tourist image, it is important to highlight the role of the local community, which is related to the concept of place belonging (Carniello et al., 2012) and can be subdivided into residents, businessmen / professionals and politicians / public management (Krippendorf, 2000). Research on community image has been conducted following two streams. On one hand, considering the active role of the residents, making the comparison between the opinions of the community and the tourists. On the other, focusing on the passive role of residents, being considered an integral part of the destination in relation to the development of local tourism and, thus, being an element that composes the local image for tourists (Chagas, 2008; Gallarza et al., 2002).

The importance of the image for the destination highlights the essentiality of image management policies in the process of planning and management of tourism development, being marketing a strategic tool for promoting the local image. In this sense, it is necessary to understand which are the

dimensions and factors responsible for the formation of the destination image in order to make possible the evaluation of the local image among the various actors of tourism to guide the decision-making process of local managers, as well as the private initiative.

Table 1 – Possible situations regarding the image of destinations

<i>Image Type</i>	<i>Characterization</i>
Overly Attractive	Those few destinations that have excessive attractiveness. There is a need for greater control and responsibility in promotion, because they may have problems supporting so many people interested in visiting it
Positive / attractive	It is that image that favors the destination. It strongly encourages tourists to come to the place. There is no need to change the image, it is only necessary to spread the word to more potential markets
Contradictory	It is the one that gives rise to different perspectives when analyzing the image
Poor / low	It is the one with low attractive potential, either due to lack of publicity or even natural/artificial resources for tourism
Neutral	The one that does not provoke any feeling of attraction or repulsion in the tourist consumer
Negative / repulsive	The one in which one or more unfavorable aspects present themselves in a more intense way than the possible favorable aspects to the target public of the destination
Mixed	That which represents a mix of attractive and repulsive components, at the same time that it arouses interest it causes feelings of uncertainty or resentment
Stereotype	Those in which some aspect of the destination has taken on great proportions to the point of becoming a type of “icon”, of representation when speaking of it
Distorted / confused	That which presents a certain overvaluation of some unfavorable aspect(s), not necessarily expressing the truth

Source: Elaborated by Chagas (2008), adapted from Bignami (2002), Mendonça Júnior (2004), Vaz (1999), Haider et al. (1994).

Dimensions and Formation of the Destination Image

Being the image of a mental and general representation that the individual conceives of a certain place, it is characterized by a great subjectivity. Its formation is influenced by personal factors such as personality, cultural values and motivations; and external stimulus factors such as word-of-mouth recommendations, advertising, among others. These factors allow the evaluation of the image in 3 dimensions (Table 2): cognitive, affective, and global.

Table 2 – Different theoretical bases that address the destination image

Image Shaper	Definition	References
Cognitive	Consists of the set of beliefs and knowledge about the destination	McCleary e Baloglu (1999)
Affective	Referring to the feelings reserved for it (destination)	McCleary e Baloglu (1999)
Global	Consists of the combination of cognitive and affective factors	Beerli e Martín (2004)
Unique	The vision of the destination as singular, unique	Qu, Kim e Im (2011)

Source: Elaborated by Arruda, Silva, and Mariani (2020), based on the work of Santana and Gosling (2017).

The cognitive image is a set of beliefs and knowledge about the destination, under the prism of rationality and logic, and can evaluate attributes about: attractions, natural environment, infrastructure and development, among others. The affective image is related to the feelings provoked by the destination: stimulating/boring; pleasant/unpleasant; exciting/boring; relaxing/stressing. From the set of cognitive and affective dimensions, the global image of the destination is created (Baloglu et al, 1999).

Qu, Kim and Im (2011) incorporated to this model the unique image dimension, which are the unique aspects capable of differentiating a given destination from others. Being considered a factor of great relevance in the composition of the overall image of the

tourist destination (Santana et al., 2018).

Still with regard to image dimensions, Echtner and Ritchie (1991) propose the existence of three continuous axes that dimension the image: the attribute-holistic, the functional-psychological, and the common-unique, as can be seen in Fig. 1. This model allows for a multidimensional understanding of the image by categorizing its components according to the set of their characteristics.

Fig. 1 – Components of the image of a tourist destination

Source: Echtner and Ritchie (1991) apud Chagas (2008)

Chagas (2008) identified theoretical models of other authors concerning the formation of the destination image. Thus, another way is to consider the image as organic and induced. The first is about the formation of the image through non-advertising sources, *i.e.*, in conversations with family members, in books, etc., besides the previous information that one already had about the destination. The second, the induced one, is the image formed by the intentional advertisements of the tourist destination promotion marketing (Gunn, 1972).

According to Gunn (1988), image formation can be divided into seven phases: the accumulation of mental images about travel experiences, modification of these images from new information, making the decision to travel, travel to the destination, participation in the destination, return home, and finally modifications of the images based on the experiences of the trip. Or, in a more simplified way, the image can also be divided only

between primary and complex, being the primary image the one formed before the tourist visits the destination, and complex, the image after the visit (Bignami, 2002).

From this theoretical presentation about the construct destination image it is possible to have a better understanding of the complexity of the theme and the objective of this research. Next, the methodology of this study will be presented.

Methodology

This is an exploratory and descriptive research of qualitative approach with data collection through bibliographic research on the theme “tourist destination image” to provide an overview of how studies on the subject are being carried out.

In order to achieve the objectives of this research, a survey of articles published in Brazil on tourist destination image was carried out using the SPELL - *Scientific Periodicals Electronic Library*, <<http://www.spell.org.br>>, which is a reference in Brazil as a repository of scientific articles in the areas of Public and Business Administration, Accounting and Tourism, maintained by ANPAD – National Association of Research and Graduate Studies in Administration.

“Spell is a system of indexing, search and free availability of scientific production, particularly in the areas of Public and Business Administration, Accounting and Tourism. With the central objective of promoting the access, organization, dissemination and analysis of the scientific production of distinct areas of knowledge, Spell fulfills a double mission: organize, in a single database, a significant collection of knowledge and provide free access to users interested in the scientific production [...]. Spell’s objectives are: organize the database of journals [...]; provide visibility to scientific production [...]; democratize access to information [...]; produce and make available Indicators of journal usage [...]; contribute so that the journals in the

database achieve high performance [...]” (SPELL, 2012)

The survey was carried out on December 21, 2021 through the advanced search options of the site for “articles” search by “document title” with the use of the keywords “destination image”, “destination image” and “tourism image”. For each term, 14, 5, and 5 were found, respectively, totaling 24 articles. The next step was to analyze the abstracts of all the articles found in order to identify those that focus on the theme tourist destination image. It was found that only 1 article (Conceição, 2020) did not fit the scope of analysis of this study and, for this reason, was excluded, for emphasizing the technical image construct. Thus, 23 articles were selected to compose this research, as can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3 – Number of articles selected for the study

<i>Keyword</i>	<i>Quantity of articles found</i>
“destination image”	14
“destination image”	5
“image tourism”	5
Total articles found	24
Excluded articles	1
Total articles selected for the study	23

Source: Own elaboration

All selected articles were read, indexed, organized, and analyzed according to the following indicators: authors, affiliation, year of publication, journal of publication, keywords, research topic, object of study, nature of the study, type of research, methodological approach, data collection method, types of sample, method of results analysis, and bibliographic references.

Analysis and Discussion of The Results

From the analysis of the 23 articles, it is found that the works were published between the years 2008 and 2020, highlighting 2018, the year with the largest number of publications on destination image, 4 articles, followed by the years 2013 and 2016 with 3 publications in each year, as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 – Number of published articles per year

Source: Own elaboration

From the analysis of Table 4, it is possible to identify that Chagas is the author with the largest number of publications, having 4 articles published between the years 2008 and 2013 (Chagas, 2008; 2009; Chagas; Marques; Duarte, 2013; Chagas; Sampaio; Santos, 2013), followed by Gosling with 3 (Machado; Gosling, 2010; Santana; Gosling, 2017; 2018). It is also observed that UFRN - Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte - is the institution with the largest number of researchers publishing on tourism destination images with a total of 5 articles. The UFMG – Federal University of Minas Gerais – follows in second with 3 articles. UFRN and UFMG are, precisely, the institutions where the authors Chagas and Gosling are linked, respectively.

According to Table 5, it can be seen that the articles that make up this study were published in 12 different Brazilian journals. The Brazilian Journal of Tourism Research is the journal with the largest number of articles published on the theme (6 articles), followed by the Virtual Journal of Tourism (3 articles).

The keyword is an important tool that allows search engines and indexers to find relevant articles on the searched topics. In the 23 articles studied, a total of 89 different keywords were used. From the analysis of Table 6 it is noted that the word “image” was used in the composition of 13 different keywords (Image Formation, Destination Image Formation, Image, Affective Image, Cognitive Image, Destination Image, Tourist Destination Image, Destination Image, Tourist Destination Image, Global Image, Tourist Image, Unique Image, Representative Images), resulting in a total of 31 mentions in the studied publications. This

reveals that there is still no consensus among scholars on the subject as to a single terminology to determine the construct tourist destination image.

Table 4 – Authors, year of publication, and affiliation

Authors	Year of publication	Affiliation ¹
Añaña, Anjos & Pereira	2016	UFPEL – UNIVALI – UNIVALI
Arruda, Silva & Mariani	2020	CEFET/RJ, UFMS e UFMS
Campos, Alexandre & Mol	2013	IFRN – UFRN – UFRN
Carniello Santaella	2012	UNITAU
Carvalho Ferreira Kanazawa Machado Giraldo	2016	USP
Chagas	2008 2009	UFRN
Chagas Marques Duarte	2013	
Chagas Sampaio Santos	2013	
Fernandes Souza Tonon Gandara	2014	UFPR
Ferreira Graciano Leal Costa	2019	UFPE
Kunz Castrogiovanni	2020	Does not mention
Lima Hardt Hardt Hardt	2020	PUC-PR
Machado Gosling	2010	UFRGS, UFMG
Martichiello Carvalho	2016	UFSCAR, UFOP
Pérez-Nebra Torres	2010	UNB
Santana Gosling	2017 2018	UFMG
Santos, Flores, Limberger	2018	IFMA, UNIVALI, UNIVALI
Santos Silva	2015	IFSP/SP
Scalabrini, Remoaldo Lourenço	2015 2018	UNIVILLE, University of Minho
Silva Souza	2018	UFPE

Source: Own elaboration

Table 5 – Journals in which the articles were published

<i>Journal</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Brazilian Journal Tourism Research [<i>Revista Brasileira de Pesquisa em Turismo</i>]	6
Tourism Virtual Notebook [<i>Caderno Virtual de Turismo</i>]	3
Tourism Journal Vision and Action [<i>Revista Turismo Visão e Ação</i>]	2
Hospitality Review [<i>Revista Hospitalidade</i>]	2
Tourism Innovation Observatory [<i>Observatório de Inovação do Turismo</i>]	2
Windrose Journal [<i>Revista Rosa dos Ventos</i>]	2
Unimep Administration Review [<i>Revista de Administração Unimep</i>]	1
Marketing & Tourism Review	1
Contemporary Administration Review [<i>Revista de Administração Contemporânea</i>]	1
FACES Journal Belo Horizonte	1
Contemporary Tourism Review [<i>Revista de Turismo Contemporâneo</i>]	1
Tourism in Analysis [<i>Turismo em Análise</i>]	1

Source: Own elaboration

Table 6 – Keywords used in the articles

<i>Keywords</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Tourist Destinations	4
Image Formation	2
Formation of the Destination Image	1
Image	5
Affective Image	2
Cognitive Image	2
Destination Image	5
Tourist destination image	3
Image of the destination	5
Tourist destination image	1
Global Image	1
Tourist image	1
Unique Image	2
Representative images	1
Tourism	7
Other words	47
TOTAL	89

Source: Own elaboration

According to Table 7, the evaluation of destination image by the tourist/visitor was the most worked theme among the studies (6 articles). This is due to the fact that destination image is a factor of paramount importance in the tourist's choice for the destination they will visit (Añaña et al., 2016; Arruda et al., 2020; Campos et al., 2013; Carvalho et al., 2016; Chagas, 2008, 2009; Chagas et al., 2013; Ferreira et al., 2019; Machado et al., 2010; Pérez-Nebra et al., 2010; Santana et al., 2017, 2018; Santos et al., 2015; Santos et al., 2018; Scalabrini et al., 2015, 2018; Carniello et al., 2012; Silva et al., 2018). In second place were studies on the development of theoretical and methodological models (4 articles). Next appear the studies reviewing and discussing the literature on destination image (3 articles). In this sense, it is possible to infer that there are still many gaps in the theories about destination image, which makes the subject a fertile territory for scientific development in the area. The image of a tourist destination is still a subject little studied by Brazilian researchers (Chagas, 2008).

In addition, according to Table 7, a total of 42 destinations were surveyed as objects of study. There was a great predominance of Brazilian cities (32 cities), especially the city of Rio de Janeiro, which was addressed in 4 articles, followed by the city of Natal-RN, studied in 2 articles. In addition, some articles chose states (2) and others, countries (3), as the object of study.

Regarding the model/theory used (Table 8) as a basis for the work carried out, it is noticed that many authors did not show the theoretical model (12 articles). This corroborates Scalabrini (2015) who found that most Brazilian publications do not point out the model used to support the study. However, when

¹ UFPEL – Universidade Federal de Pelotas, UNIVALI – Universidade do Vale do Itajaí, CEFET/RJ – Centro Federal de Educação Tecnológica Celso Suckow da Fonseca, UFMS – Universidade Federal do Mato Grosso do Sul, IFRN – Instituto Federal do Rio Grande do Norte, UFRN – Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte, UNITAU – Universidade de Taubaté, USP – Universidade de São Paulo, UFPR – Universidade Federal do Paraná, UFPE – Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, PUC-PR – Pontifícia Universidade Católica do Paraná, UFRGS – Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, UFMG – Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais, UFSCAR – Universidade Federal de São Carlos, UFOP – Universidade Federal de Ouro Preto, UNB – Universidade de Brasília, IFMA – Instituto Federal de Educação, Ciência e Tecnologia do Maranhão, IFSP/SP – Instituto Federal de Educação, Ciência e Tecnologia de São Paulo

analyzing the articles that evidenced the theoretical model it is noted the use of models developed by international authors such as Echtner and Ritchie (1991), Mcclery and Baloglu (1999), Beerli and Martín (2004) and Qu, Kim and Im (2011), among others.

Table 7 – Themes and objects of the studies

<i>Subject of the study</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Evaluation of the destination image by the tourist/visitor	6
Development of a theoretical/methodological model of destination image	4
Review and discussion of the literature on destination image	3
Relationship of the landscapes with the destination image	2
Assessment of the destination image by the resident and tourist	2
Influence websites on the destination's image	1
Formation of the destination image	1
The influence of image on satisfaction and loyalty	1
Influence of terrorist attacks on the destination's image	1
Image of World Heritage destinations	1
Resident's evaluation of the destination image	1
Total	23
Cities (Rio de Janeiro, Natal, Fortaleza, Ouro Preto, Salvador, among others)	32
States/DF (Rio Grande do Norte and Brasília)	2
Countries (Brazil and Iceland)	3
Not Applied	5
Total	42

Source: Own elaboration

Table 8 – Models and theories used in the articles

<i>Model / Theory used</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Not evidenced	12
Experience Theory (Pine and Gilmore, 1998) and the new service logic (Vargo & Lusch, 2004)	1
Indicator evaluation (PINTO, 2010; CHAGAS; DANTAS, 2008)	1
Online experience evaluation categories: information content, ease of use, visual attractiveness, and overall online experience, as per Gao and Bai (2014)	1
Beerli and Martin (2004b)	1
Chi and Qu Model (2008)	1
Crompton (1992); Prayag (2008)	1
Echtner e Ritchie (1991)	1
Gunn (1972) and Echtner and Ritchie (1991)	1
Mcclery and Baloglu (1999), Beerli and Martín (2004) and Qu, Kim and Im (2011)	1
Ahmed(1991); Baloglu (2001); Beerli; Martín (2004); Buosi; Leocádio (2013); Chagas; Marques Júnior; Duarte (2013); Frías; Rodríguez; Castañeda (2008); Mcclery; Baloglu (1999); Qu; Kim; Im (2011); Santos; Cruz (2013); Suárez; José (2011); Qu; Suárez; José (2011); Yacout; Hefny (2015)	1
Hofstede's cultural dimensions (1980)	1
Total	23

Source: Own elaboration

As for the methodological profile (Table 9), 11 of the 23 articles are characterized as exploratory-descriptive research, most of them being empirical in nature (12 articles), balancing between quantitative (10 articles) and qualitative (10 articles) methodological approaches, with only 3 articles using a qualitative-quantitative approach.

Table 9 – Methodological characteristics

<i>Type of survey</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Nature of study</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Methodological approach</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Exploratory-descriptive	11	Empirical	12	Quantitative	10
Not evidenced	6	Theoretical	6	Qualitative	10
Descriptive	3	Theoretical and Empirical	5	Qualiquantitative	3
Exploratory	2				
Pre-experimentall	1				
Total	23	Total	23	Total	23

Source: Own elaboration

Table 10 shows that questionnaires (9 articles) and bibliographic research (5 articles) are the main forms of data collection used and the type of sample is non-probabilistic by convenience in most Brazilian research on tourist

destination image. This may reveal that, although half of the studies define themselves as quantitative research, there is a lack of probability samples (only 3 articles) capable of statistically representing the populations studied.

Table 10 – Types of data collection and sampling

<i>Data Collection</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Sample Type</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Questionnaire	9	Non-probabilistic by convenience	13
Bibliographic research	5	Not applicable	6
Survey	2	Probabilistic, simple random	3
Interviews	2	Not evidenced	1
Netnography	1		
Direct observation, bibliographic and documentary research	1		
Questionnaire and debriefing	1		
Documentary research and interviews	1		
Discussion Groups	1		
Total	23	Total	23

Source: Own elaboration

In contrast to the lack of probabilistic samples, the methods used for data analysis reveal complex descriptive and multivariate statistical procedures, such as Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), Multidimensional Scaling (ASCAL), Multiple Linear Regression Analysis (MLR), among others (Table 11).

When analyzing the bibliographic references used in the 23 articles it was found that a total of 782 different publications were referenced. They are works that address the most diverse themes and areas of study due to the complexity of the tourist destination image construct. Thus, publications from the areas of tourism, administration, marketing, geography, sociology, and statistics, among others, were found. However, the most frequently cited works were the specific ones about the theme destination image.

From Table 12, we conclude that most Brazilian authors have as theoretical basis for the study of the theme foreign authors, such as: Baloglu and MacCleary (1999) who were cited in 13 of the 23 articles analyzed; Echtner and Ritchie (1991), referenced in 12 articles and; Gallarza, Saura and García (2002), cited in 11 articles. Beerli and Martín (2004), other foreign researchers, referenced in 7 articles. Then comes Chagas (2008), the first Brazilian on the list, cited in 7 articles.

Table 11 – Data analysis methodologies

<i>Data Analysis</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Extensive review and discussion of the specific literature	4
Content Analysis	3
Descriptive statistical analyses, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and the Multiple Linear Regression Analysis (MLR)	2
Empirical analysis, direct observation	2
Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA); Multidimensional Scaling (ASCAL)	1
Word Cloud and Descending Hierarchical Classification (DHC) – Iramuteq software	1
Kendall's correlation analysis	1
Content analysis and statistical analysis	1
Not evidenced	1
Structural Equation Modeling	1
Factorability analyses. The validation process was Item Response Theory [IRT]	1
Compilation of the eleven hypotheses presented and discussed	1
Descriptive and multivariate statistical procedures. Exploratory Factor Analysis and Cluster Analysis	1
Statistical techniques of ordinal logistic regression for ranking data, multidimensional scaling and scatter diagram	1
Comparison of interviews and documents	1
Descriptive Analysis	1
Total	23

Source: Own elaboration

Table 12 – Main references used in the articles

<i>Bibliographic Reference</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Baloglu, S., & Mcclary, K. (1999)	13
Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. R. B. (1991)	12
Gallarza, M. G., Saura, I. G., & García, H. C. (2002)	11
Beerli, A.; Martín, J.D. (2004)	7
Chagas, Márcio Marreiro das. (2008)	7
Chagas, M. M. (2009)	6
Chagas, M. M. das, Marques, Jr. S., & Duarte, A. C. F. (2013)	6
Chi, C. G., & Qu, H. (2008)	6
Bignami, Rosana Viana De Sá (2002)	5
Chagas, M. M. das, & Dantas, A. V. S. (2008)	5
Chen, C.F., & Tsai, D. (2007)	5
Crompton, J. (1979)	5
Gandara, José Manuel Gonçalves (2008)	5
Pérez-Nebra, A. R. (2005)	5
Valls, Josep Francesc (1996)	5
Assael, Henry (1999)	4
Chagas, M. M. das, & Dantas, A. V. S. (2009)	4
Chagas, M. M. das, Sampaio, L. M. B., & Santos, K. E. B. (2013)	4
Fakeye, P., & Crompton, J. (1991)	4
Gunn, C. (1988)	4
O'Neil, Isobel (2006)	4
Pike, S. (2002)	4

Source: Own elaboration

Chagas has a very expressive amount of publications on tourist destination image with 10 referenced works, as can be seen in Table 13. Chagas (2008) was used as bibliographic reference in 7 articles and is a theoretical study that makes a broad review and discussion of specialized literature on destination image and suggests a proposed typology of studies on the subject. In the sequence, there is the article Chagas (2009) that served as references for 6 articles. This is another theoretical study, but makes a discussion of the main international models on the formation of the image of tourist destinations. And, in third, the article by Chagas, Marques Jr. and Duarte (2013) (referenced in 6 articles), of theoretical-empirical nature, which makes the analysis of the image formation process of sun and beach tourist destinations. All these mentioned works by Chagas are part of the set of

articles selected for this study, with the inclusion of Chagas, Sampaio and Santos (2013), which had not yet been mentioned and is also part of the analyzed scope. The latter is a theoretical-empirical study that analyzes the influence of destination image on tourist satisfaction and loyalty.

Table 13 – Chagas' Bibliographical References used in the articles

<i>Bibliographic Reference</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Chagas, M. M. das (2008)	7
Chagas, M. M. (2009)	6
Chagas, M. M. das, Marques Jr. S., & Duarte, A. C. F. (2013)	6
Chagas, M. M. das, & Dantas, A.V.S. (2008)	5
Chagas, M. M. das, & Dantas, A.V.S. (2009)	4
Chagas, M. M. das, Sampaio, L. M. B., & Santos, K. E. B. (2013).	4
Chagas, M. M., & Marques Jr. S. (2010)	3
Chagas, M. M. (2010)	2
Chagas, M. M. das (2007)	2
Chagas, M. M., & Brandao, P. de M. (2008)	1

Source: Own elaboration

From the analysis of the bibliographical references, it is possible to conclude that the main publications that serve as a basis for studies on the image of tourist destinations are: Baloglu and Macclearly (1999); Echtner and Ritchie (1991); Gallarza, Saura and García (2002); Beerli and Martín (2004); and Chagas (2008). According to this research, Chagas can be considered as the main Brazilian reference in the study of the theme.

Final Considerations

In order to provide an overview of how the studies on the theme tourist destination image are being carried out, a systematic review of the specific literature on the subject was conducted. To this end, the SPELL platform was used, where 23 articles were found to compose the scope of analysis of this study. The articles were published between the years 2008 and 2020. The Brazilian Journal of Tourism Research is the journal with the largest number of articles published on the subject. Moving on to the analysis of the authors, Chagas and Gosling are the authors with the

largest number of publications among the articles that make up this research, being affiliated with UFRN and UFMG, respectively.

From the analysis of the key words used to enable the search in indexers it was noted that the word “image” was used in the composition of 13 different keywords, revealing that there is still no consensus as to a single terminology to determine the tourist destination image construct. In relation to the theme of the study it was found that the evaluation of the destination image by the tourist/visitor was the most researched theme, being Brazilian cities the main objects of study. The theoretical models developed by international authors such as Echtner and Ritchie (1991), McCleary and Baloglu (1999), Beerli and Martín (2004) were the main models used in the articles.

As for the methodological profile, it can be said that most of the articles studied are characterized as exploratory-descriptive research, of an empirical nature, balancing

between quantitative and qualitative methodological approaches, with data collection through questionnaires and bibliographic research, and predominance of the use of a non-probability convenience sample. The methods used for data analysis reveal complex statistical procedures.

When analyzing the bibliographic references used in the articles, the main publications that serve as a basis for destination image studies were identified: Baloglu and McCleary (1999); Echtner and Ritchie (1991); Gallarza, Saura and García (2002); Beerli and Martín (2004) and Chagas (2008).

The results of this study seek to contribute to the scientific development about the tourist destination image, serving as a basis to guide future studies on the subject and, consequently, contributing to the development of tourist destinations. After all, the image that a tourist has of a destination is a determining factor in his choice of the place he will visit.

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